

Synthesis and Characterisation of some Bis(dithiocarbamato)-oxovanadium(II) and their Adducts with Soft Lewis Acids

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Several new bi(dithiocarbamato)oxovanadium(II) of the formula, VO(dtc)₂, have been prepared and characterised on the basis of analytical and spectral data. Their interaction with soft acceptors has yielded molecular adducts of the formula, VO(dtc)₂.2M'X, or VO(dtc)₂.2MX, where M' = Hg or Cd; M' = Ag, X = Cl, SCN, OCOCF₃ and OClO₃.

In recent years, metal^{1,2} and organometal dithiocarbamates^{3,4} have attracted attention of a number of workers, but only a few reports have appeared on the corresponding derivatives containing oxometal moieties. Molybdenyl⁵ and a few vanadyl⁶ dithiocarbamates have been reported. The communication deals with the synthesis and characterisation of some new bis(dithiocarbamato)oxovanadium(II) and their adducts with some soft metal acceptors. A number of new bimetallic derivatives having bridging dithiocarbamate groups have been obtained. Characterisation and structural assessment have been made from the results of physico-chemical studies.

Experimental

Oxovanadium(II) sulphate (Fluka) was converted to the corresponding dihydroxide VO(OH)₂ by treating with aqueous ammonia solution⁷. Carbon disulphide (B.D.H.), amines, 2,2'-dimethoxypropane and triethylorthoformate (Aldrich) were distilled/recrystallised before use. The solvents were purified by conventional methods.

Vanadium and other metals were determined gravimetrically by the reported methods⁸. Elemental analysis (C, H and N), IR spectra (4000–200 cm⁻¹) using a PR 200 spectrophotometer and electronic spectra (methanol) were determined at the Central Drug Research Institute, Lucknow. The molar conductances of the complexes (10⁻³ M solution) in DMSO were measured at room temperature using a Phillips PR 9500 magic eye bridge. Magnetic susceptibilities were determined at room temperature by Gouy method.

Bis(dithiocarbamato)oxovanadium(II): The title compounds were prepared by insertion of CS₂ between oxovanadium hydroxide and amines using 2,2'-dimethoxypropane or triethyl orthoformate as the solvent. In a typical experiment, to a mixture of (10 mmol) of freshly prepared hydrated oxovanadium(II) hydroxide (20 mmol) and carbon

disulphide suspended in 2,2'-dimethoxypropane (~25 ml) was added morpholine (20 mmol) in the same solvent (20 ml) at -20° with constant stirring. The reaction mixture was further stirred for several hours. The precipitated bis(dithiocarbamato)oxovanadium(II) was filtered, washed with diethyl ether and dried over P₄O₁₀ in vacuum. Identical products were prepared by treating oxovanadium(II) sulphate with ammonium salts of dithiocarbamic acid.

Bimetallic dithiocarbamates: The bimetallic adducts were prepared by the direct reaction of bis(dithiocarbamato)oxovanadium(II) with soft Lewis acids, such as Hg^{II}, Cd^{II} and Ag^I salts. In a typical experiment, to a stirring methanolic solution of bis(dithiocarbamato)oxovanadium(II) (10 mmol) was added HgCl₂ (20 mmol) in acetone-methanol (1 : 1, 25 ml). The reaction mixture was stirred for ~10 h. The precipitated product was washed several times with acetone/methanol (1 : 1) mixture and dried over P₄O₁₀ in vacuum. Similar adducts were prepared using Hg(SCN)₂, Hg(OClO₃)₂, Hg(OCOFCF₃), CdCl₂, AgSCN, AgOClO₃ and AgOCOFCF₃ as acceptors.

Results and Discussion

Oxovanadium(II) dithiocarbamates have been prepared according to equation (1),

The products (Table 1) having 1 : 2 (metal-dtc) stoichiometry are green to grey in colour. They are stable under dry nitrogen or in vacuum over P₄O₁₀. They are insoluble in common organic solvents, sparingly soluble in methanol but soluble in DMSO or DMF. The molar conductances in DMSO show their non-electrolytic nature. The magnetic moments lie in the range 1.69–1.73 B.M. corresponding to one unpaired electron.

In the electronic spectra of oxovanadium compounds, a three band spectrum for five coordinate

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL DATA AND CHARACTERISTIC IR BANDS OF BIS(DITHIOCARBAMATO)OXOVANADIUM(II)

Compd.	M.p. °C	Yield %	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)				ν_{max} (cm ⁻¹)			
			V	O	H	N	O-N	O=S	V=O	V-S
VO[S(S)CN(C ₂ H ₅) ₂] ₂	136	80	13.9 (14.0)	32.9 (33.0)	5.4 (5.5)	7.6 (7.7)	1 430m	1 020s	960sbr	355m
VO[S(S)CNHC ₄ H ₉] ₂	145	85	14.0 (14.0)	32.9 (33.0)	5.4 (5.5)	7.6 (7.7)	1 425m	1 020s	960sbr	357m
VO[S(S)CN(C ₆ H ₅) ₂] ₂	162	80	10.6 (10.7)	45.4 (45.4)	7.5 (7.5)	5.8 (5.8)	1 430m	1 015s	965sbr	357m
VO[S(S)CN(C ₆ H ₅) ₂] ₂	180	84	9.1 (9.1)	56.1 (56.2)	3.5 (3.6)	5.0 (5.0)	1 435m	1 025s	960sbr	355m
VO[S(S)CN(CH ₂ .C ₆ H ₅) ₂] ₂	145	80	8.3 (8.3)	58.7 (58.9)	4.4 (4.5)	4.5 (4.5)	1 425m	1 020s	965sbr	354m
VO[S(S)CNHC ₄ H ₉] ₂	163	80	12.5 (12.6)	41.6 (41.6)	2.8 (2.9)	6.3 (6.4)	1 430m	1 020s	958sbr	353m
VO[S(S)CNC ₄ H ₉ O] ₂	136	95	12.9 (13.0)	30.6 (30.6)	4.0 (4.0)	7.0 (7.1)	1 430m	1 020s	962sbr	355m
VO[S(S)CNC ₄ H ₉] ₂	110	94	14.1 (14.2)	33.3 (33.4)	4.3 (4.4)	7.6 (7.7)	1 425m	1 025s	962sbr	356m
VO[S(S)CNC ₄ H ₉ O] ₂	110	92	13.1 (12.1)	37.1 (37.2)	5.0 (5.1)	7.1 (7.2)	1 430m	1 015s	960sbr	356m
VO[S(S)CNC ₄ H ₉ O]CNC ₄ H ₉ O] ₂	148	96	9.3 (9.4)	48.7 (48.7)	4.7 (4.8)	10.2 (10.3)	1 425m	1 020s	955sbr	355m

TABLE 2—ANALYTICAL DATA AND CHARACTERISTIC IR BANDS OF VO[S(S)CNC₄H₉O]₂.2M'X₂ OR 2MX

M'X ₂ /MX	M.p. °C	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)				ν_{max} (cm ⁻¹)				
		V	Metal	O	H	N	O=N	O=S	V=O	V-S
2HgCl ₂	199d	5.3 (5.4)	42.8 (42.8)	12.7 (12.8)	1.6 (1.7)	2.9 (3.0)	1 470m	1 005s	960sbr	355m
2Hg(SCN) ₂	165d	4.9 (4.9)	39.0 (39.1)	16.3 (16.4)	1.5 (1.5)	8.1 (8.2)	1 465m	1 005s	962sbr	357m
2CdCl ₂	>240	6.1 (6.2)	27.6 (27.6)	14.6 (14.7)	2.2 (2.3)	3.3 (3.4)	1 468m	1 005s	958sbr	353m
2AgSCN	172d	7.0 (7.0)	29.7 (29.8)	19.8 (19.9)	2.1 (2.2)	7.6 (7.7)	1 475m	1 005s	960sbr	354m
2Hg(OCIO ₂) ₂	205d	4.1 (4.2)	33.5 (33.6)	—	—	—	1 473m	1 005s	955sbr	355m
2Hg(OCOCF ₃) ₂	174d	4.0 (4.1)	32.1 (32.1)	—	—	—	1 468m	1 005s	958sbr	353m
2AgOCOCF ₃	187d	6.0 (6.1)	25.8 (25.9)	—	—	—	1 470m	1 005s	960sbr	353m
2AgOCIO ₂	>240	6.2 (6.3)	26.7 (26.7)	—	—	—	1 468m	1 005s	965sbr	355m

complex possessing an effective C_{4v} symmetry and a square-pyramidal shape has been suggested. Bis(dithiocarbamato)oxovanadium(II) also exhibits three electronic spectral bands in the region 12 000–12 500, 15 000–16 000 and 22 000–22 500 cm⁻¹ which closely resemble those observed in other five-coordinate oxovanadium(II) complexes and are assigned to d_{xy}→d_{xz}, d_{yz}, d_{xy}→d_{x²-y²} and d_{xy}→d_{z²} transitions, respectively. Two additional intense bands appearing in the range 33 000–33 500 and 37 000–37 500 cm⁻¹ are due to intra-ligand transitions and are assigned to π→π* transitions⁹. The absence of splitting suggests the chelating behaviour of the dithiocarbamate groups¹⁰.

The infrared spectra of bis(dithiocarbamato)oxovanadium(II) show strong bands due to ν_{C=S} located at 1 020±5 cm⁻¹ suggesting the presence of chelated dithiocarbamate groups¹¹. The absorp-

tion at ca 1 430±5 cm⁻¹ assigned to ν_{C=N}, is characteristic of thiouride band having partial double bond character¹². Absorptions at 960±5 cm⁻¹ and 355±3 cm⁻¹ are assigned to terminal ν_{V=O} and ν_{V-S} modes of vibrations respectively. A possible structure for bis(dithiocarbamato)oxovanadium(II) (R refers to Table 1) may be as follows,

In the spectra of the bimetallic complexes, bis-VO[S(S)CNC₄H₉O]₂.2M'X₂ or 2MX (M=Ag; M'=Hg or Cd; X=Cl, SCN, OCOCF₃ or OCIO₂), the presence of unsplit bands due to ν_{C=S} and

$\nu_{C=N}$ at $1\ 005 \pm 2$ and $1\ 460 \pm 5$ cm^{-1} , respectively, indicates bonding from both the sulphur atoms of dtc—one of which is bonded to vanadium while the other to the soft metal acceptors. Due to the formation of new coordinate bands, an electron drift from the organyl group (R) takes place resulting in an increase of the double bond character of C=N and decrease in the C=S bond order. The former therefore shows a distinct upward shift while the latter undergoes negative shift. Vanadium metal associated modes of vibration $\nu_{V=O}$ and ν_{V-S} remain unaltered in the adducts. The thiocyanate group is S-bonded to the soft metal in $\text{VO}[\text{S}(\text{S})\text{CNC}_4\text{H}_8\text{O}]_2$.

$2\text{Hg}(\text{SCN})_2$, since $\nu_{C=N}$, $\nu_{C=S}$, δ_{NCS} appear at 2 060, 720 and 470 cm^{-1} , respectively¹³. The trifluoroacetate groups in $\text{VO}[\text{S}(\text{S})\text{CNC}_4\text{H}_8\text{O}]_2 \cdot 2\text{AgOCOCF}_3$

are unidentate as $\nu_{\text{as}} \text{OCO}$ and $\nu_{\text{sym}} \text{OCO}$ appear at 1 690 and 1 430 cm^{-1} , respectively¹⁴, having $\Delta\nu = 260$ cm^{-1} ($-\Delta\nu = \nu_{\text{as}} \text{OCO} - \nu_{\text{sym}} \text{OCO}$). The perchlorate group in $\text{VO}[\text{S}(\text{S})\text{CNC}_4\text{H}_8\text{O}]_2 \cdot 2\text{Hg}$

$(\text{OClO}_3)_2$ is unidentately coordinated (C_{3v} symmetry) as $\nu_{\text{sym}} \text{Cl-O}$, $\nu_{\text{sym}} \text{ClO}_3$, $\delta_{\text{as}} \text{Cl-O}$, $\delta_{\text{s}} \text{ClO}_3$ and $\delta_{\text{asym}} \text{ClO}_3$ are located at 910, 1 040, 1 130, 690 and 620 cm^{-1} , respectively.

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